

Effect of Testing Conditions on Low-Cycle Fatigue Behaviour of Non-Stabilizing Steels

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ABSTRACT

The research presents the results of low-cycle fatigue tests performed for two materials: P91 and S420M steels. Both materials exhibit continuous cyclic softening, without a period of cyclic properties stabilisation. The influence on durability of the following testing conditions was investigated: control variable (stress or strain) and creep periods, applied in several combinations with fatigue loading. In the case of S420M steel samples, both undeformed and pre-strained specimens were used. The influence of pre-straining on durability was analysed.

Keywords: low cycle fatigue, cyclic softening, fatigue damage

1 INTRODUCTION

Many steel grades exhibit continuous cyclic softening without the period of cyclic properties stabilization, regardless of the testing temperature and strain amplitude. For these steels, it is difficult to design experimental tests for various types of control so that their results are comparable. Usually, for stress-controlled tests, the stress amplitude is set from half a lifetime of the strain-controlled case. In general, the selected test conditions should depend on the intended use of the structural element and the expected load type. However, strain controlled experimental fatigue tests are most often performed, to avoid the material flow observed during stress controlled tests. This may result in erroneous fatigue life predictions if testing conditions (constant strain amplitude) influence the fatigue properties, and the experimental load type does not correspond to the operation mode of considered mechanical facilities, cf (1).

In the present paper the experimental research is described, indicating the influence of P91 and S420M steel testing conditions (stress or strain control) on chosen hysteresis loop characteristics. It is shown that the Ramberg-Osgood stress-strain curves for strain-controlled fatigue tests do not coincide with curves obtained at constant stress amplitude, while the differences are more pronounced at elevated temperatures. Another part of the research consists in presenting the impact of initial deformation on the fatigue life of structural elements, on the example of S420M steel specimens. Many technical objects (for example bridges) may be subjected to occasional significant static loads during operation. The effects of such unforeseen events in the form of initial deformations are usually not taken into account in fatigue calculations, which are most often based on material characteristics determined experimentally using as-received materials. S420M steel is very often used for welded elements that are subjected to very high static and fatigue loads. Typical applications for S420M steel are bridges, viaducts, long-span structures, high-rise buildings and other engineering structures. Due to frequent cases of overloads of these types of objects, tests are necessary to determine their impact on the fatigue life of S420M steel (2).

The third factor considered in this work that influences the fatigue life is creep. To indicate the interaction between fatigue and creep, different combinations of fatigue and creep loading are investigated. It is shown that fatigue life predictions that do not regard the material damage due to creep, may lead to a significant overestimation of durability, cf (3-4). Taking into account the creep damage in the calculations improves the compliance of the numerical and experimental results.

2 TESTED MATERIALS

Two steel grades were subject to testing. The first set of tests was performed on P91 steel specimens cut out of a boiler pipe. The chemical composition of steel is shown in *Table 1*.

Table 1. The chemical composition of the steel.

C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Mo	Al	Co	Cu	Nb	Ti	V	W
0,197	0,442	0,489	0,017	0,005	8,802	0,307	0,012	0,017	0,036	0,074	0,004	0,201	0,02

In the second set of experimental tests, specimens made of S420M steel sheet with a thickness of 30 mm were considered. *Table 2* summarizes the chemical composition of S420M steel.

Table 2. Chemical composition of S420M steel (wt %)

Fe	C	Si	Mn	P	Cr	Al	Nb	Ti	V	W
98.0	0.125	0.215	1.45	0.0135	0.0208	0.0268	0.0288	0.013	0.0519	0.0150

Specimens were prepared in accordance with standards ASTM E606-92 (5), ASTM E8 (6), and ASTM E466-21 (7).

3 TESTING CONDITIONS

The following test types were performed to investigate the effect of testing conditions on low-cycle fatigue behaviour of non-stabilizing steels: (a) strain controlled low cycle fatigue tests (see *Figure 1a*), (b) stress controlled low cycle fatigue tests (see *Figure 1b*), (c) fatigue alternating with creep, in a different order of events (creep then fatigue *Figure 1c*, fatigue then creep *Figure 1d*, fatigue with dwell in each cycle *Figure 1e*).

Fig. 1. Load schemes: (a) strain controlled fatigue; (b) stress controlled fatigue; (c) creep then fatigue; (d) fatigue then creep; (e) fatigue with dwell in each cycle

4 TEST RESULTS

4.1 Fatigue tests

Both P91 and S420M steels considered in this paper belong to materials that do not exhibit a period of cyclic properties stabilisation. The experimental data (see *Figure 2*) indicate that the tested steels

exhibits cyclic softening, regardless of the testing temperature and strain amplitude. The initial rapid softening phase is followed by the slow quasi-linear softening, and finally again fast softening that ultimately leads to failure of the tested sample.

Fig. 2. Maximum stress on cycle: (a) P91 steel, strain controlled, strain amplitude equal 0.6; (b) S420M steel, as-received material; (c) S420M steel, pre-strained material

The stress-controlled tests were also carried out, for the stress amplitudes determined based on the experiment results at the constant strain amplitude. In the absence of the stabilization period, to establish comparable test conditions, stress amplitudes were taken from the middle-cycle of each strain-controlled test ($n/N = 0.5$), cf (1). Test results were analysed in the context of the impact of load conditions (in the case of P91 steel specimens), and additionally initial strains (for specimens made of S420M steel) on both durability and hysteresis loop properties. The analytical relationship between stress amplitude σ_a and plastic strain amplitude ε_{ap} of the form proposed in ASTM E606-92 (5) was adopted:

$$\log \sigma_a = \log K' + n' \log \varepsilon_{ap} \quad (1)$$

The results of fatigue life were presented in the form of graphs in the $2N_f - \varepsilon$ coordinate system. Fatigue graphs in the bi-logarithmic scale (Figures 3 and 4) were approximated by the equation of the following form, cf (5):

$$\frac{\Delta \varepsilon_t}{2} = \frac{\Delta \varepsilon_e}{2} + \frac{\Delta \varepsilon_p}{2} = \frac{\sigma_f'}{E} (2N_f)^b + \varepsilon_f' (2N_f)^c \quad (2)$$

It was observed that the durability is affected by the test conditions. For both materials, all test temperatures and all load levels, in the conditions of stress control the fatigue life is noticeably lower than the fatigue life obtained in the conditions of strain control (see Figures 3 and 4). For example, for a P91 steel sample subjected to low cycle fatigue at the elevated temperature of 600°C, the number of cycles to failure is 1.63 times higher under strain control (with the strain amplitude $\varepsilon_{at} = 0.003$) than the number of cycles to failure under stress control (see Figure 3, cf. (1)).

Fig. 3. Fatigue curves for P91 steel subjected to low-cycle fatigue at temperature of 600°C presented in bi-logarithmic scale (after (8)).

Fig. 4. Fatigue curves for S420M steel subjected to low-cycle fatigue at room temperature: (a) as-received material; (b) as-received and pre-strained material (pre-strain value $\varepsilon=10\%$), strain controlled tests; (c) as-received and pre-strained material (pre-strain value $\varepsilon=10\%$), stress controlled tests

Under the conditions of controlled stress ($\sigma_a = \text{const}$), as expected, cyclic creep of the sample material was observed. The phenomenon consisted in the shift of the hysteresis loops along the strain axis, increasing the maximum strain on a cycle ε_{max} . Figure 5 shows exemplary hysteresis loops for P91 (Figure 5a) and S340M (Figure 5b) steel samples.

Fig. 5. Exemplary hysteresis loops recorded in fatigue tests a) P91 steel, $T=20^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\sigma_a=510\text{ MPa}$; b) S420M steel, $T=600^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\sigma_a=225\text{ MPa}$.

Pre-deformation of the specimens affects the low-cycle properties both in stress-controlled and strain-controlled test conditions. *Figure 4a* and *4b* shows diagrams illustrating the results of tests carried out in accordance with ASTM E606-92 under strain and stress control conditions. It is well visible that at the same strain amplitude levels, the durability of specimens subjected to initial deformation is always higher than that of as-received specimens.

4.2 Creep/fatigue tests

Figure 6 shows the course of energy accumulation for two stress levels, realized under the conditions of a cyclic load only (*f*), and a cyclic load preceded by a creep load (*c-f*), for a P91 steel specimens (see *Figure 1c*). Additionally, the critical value of dissipated energy $W_{pl}(N)$ is presented in the figure. Under the (*c-f*) program conditions, the energy accumulation in the fatigue part starts from the value of the energy dissipated in the creep test (W_c), which is relatively low. Based on the results, it can be concluded that the total values of the energy ($W_t = W_c + W_f$) for the samples under the conditions of (*c-f*) loads are very close to the boundary diagram for pure fatigue test.

During the implementation of the opposite load variant (*f-c*) (see *Figure 1d*), the accumulation of the dissipated energy in the whole (*f-c*) test is different. The accumulation of plastic strain energy in the (*f*) part of the test is then followed until failure by the accumulation of creep energy (see *Figure 6b*). The whole curves *1* and *5* correspond to the energy plots in pure fatigue conditions. In the indicated points, the load switches from fatigue to creep, and the cumulative energy paths switch from *1* to *1'*, and from *5* to *5'*. The critical values of the total dissipated energy at failure appear to be much lower than in the case of a pure fatigue load test.

In *Figure 6b* it can be seen that the critical values of the dissipated energy during the (*f-c*) program are definitely below the limit line indicated in *Figure 6a*. The values of the dissipated energy during the implementation of two load variants (*c-f* and *f-c*, see *Figure 1c* and *1d*) are compared in *Table 3*. A significant effect of the load sequence on both the critical energy and the total number of cycles is observed. Based on the above results, it can be concluded that the creep/fatigue load sequence has a significant impact on the sample durability. Preceding a fatigue load with a constant load (*c-f* program) causes a reduction in fatigue life concerning the test in which creep is preceded by fatigue. The third creep/fatigue load scheme was realized according to the scheme shown in *Figure 1e*, with a dwell time τ applied in each load cycle. During the experimental tests a very clear effect of the dwell time on the fatigue life was observed. The fatigue life experimental results obtained for various load program sequences are summarized in *Figure 7* in the form of fatigue diagrams. The durability results at four stress levels were approximated in the semi-logarithmic coordinate system by a regression equation of the form:

$$\sigma_a = a \log N + b \quad (1)$$

It can be observed that with the increase of time τ the fatigue life decreases.

Table 3. Total energy W_t and total number of cycles depending on the load program.

σ_a MPa	Energy MJ/m ³			
	Load Variant (c-f)		Load Variant (f-c)	
	W_t	N	W_t	N
219	4423.8	6116	2208.3	9991
225	2910.0	2046	1471.7	5858
240	2358.1	1743	1047.3	3163
249	2160.4	939	738.7	1327
258	1737.5	639	495.6	795

Fig. 6. Energy accumulation in the course of (a) (c-f) and (f) tests; (b) (f-c) test.

Fig. 7. Durability results (experiment, P91 steel): a) fatigue curves, b) summary of durability results (after

5 CONCLUSIONS

Some steel materials widely used in engineering applications do not exhibit stabilisation of cyclic properties during fatigue tests. This makes it difficult to design experimental tests under various control conditions in such a way that their results are comparable. A commonly used rule is that the stress amplitude is set as the maximum stress in the middle cycle of the strain-controlled test. It was shown in this research that such procedure results in significant differences in durability assessments based on the classical stress or strain based approaches, and the descriptions based on the dissipated energy should be applied.

Another source of errors in estimating fatigue life lies in disregarding the effects of permanent loads causing creep. Not only the permanent loads themselves, but also their sequence in combination with

cyclic loads influence the durability, which is a manifestation of the coupling between creep and fatigue. Therefore, the linear damage summation rules should be used with caution. Finally, one should be aware of the possibility of pre-loads and their impact on the fatigue life. In the case of S420M steel considered in this research, the pre-straining improves durability.

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